

THE CREATING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT KARAKALPAK SCHOOLS

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Summary: In the thesis deals with the methods of teaching Russian, English, German and French in the conditions of Karakalpakstan are given. The adoption of a number of decisions to improve the study of foreign languages has expanded the methodological basis for the teaching of foreign languages in educational institutions in Karakalpakstan.

Keywords: German, education, French, school, Russian, English.

The creating of foreign language is an important task of the state policy of our country. In the context of the transition to the information stage of the development of a society based on information technologies and knowledge, education is becoming an essential resource for socio-economic and political development. The introduction of new teaching and methodological concepts, educational and methodological kits and other means of training increase the level of education, including to foreign languages. The attention paid by the State to the upbringing of the younger generation has led to the development of the education system as a whole. Teaching methods are an essential part of the foreign language learning process. The main groups of methods in the history of foreign language teaching methods are: translation (grammar-translation and vocabulary-translation); Direct and natural methods and their modifications; the mixed methods; Conscious-comparative and conscious-practical methods; activity and personal and communicative methods. In the middle of the 20th century, in the schools of Karakalpakstan, the process of

teaching the Russian language, according to the resolution of the NSC of the USSR and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Ukraine (b) "On Compulsory Study of the Russian Language in Schools of National Republics and Regions" of March 13, 1938, mainly used translation methods. On May 27, 1961, the Government Decree "On improving the study of foreign languages" was adopted, according to which it was planned to create 700 special schools and write new textbooks for the study of foreign language, including for national languages. The decree allowed the teaching of foreign language in kindergartens and primary schools. It was suggested that the curricula of universities, especially in humanitarian fields, should be changed so that graduates were fluent in foreign languages. During this period, the methodological base of foreign language education expanded. Methods based on active work of thinking, on development of sense guess, which were based on audio-linguistic technique of skills, appear.

During this period, a state order was formed for the production of records with foreign language lessons, the purchase of foreign educational films, the creation of special TV shows, the production of dictionaries and books of foreign classics in the languages of the original. In the conditions of Karakalpakstan this method did not have a wide possibility, as schools lacked not only educational films and plates, it was rare to have technical devices themselves.

The expansion of communication horizons makes it possible today to deepen intercultural relations and defines new prospects for educational and methodological tools for teaching foreign languages throughout the structure of educational institutions of Karakalpakstan.

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